

Torque and Shear Stress Distributions in Arterial Wall with Torsion around the Vessel Axis

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Abstract

We analyze shear stress distributions in an arterial wall and torques with torsion around the vessel axis depending on the axial stretch ratio. A Riemannian stress-free configuration of artery is adopted to analyze stress distributions. It is determined from experimentally investigated deformations of arterial ring radially cut and axial strip sectioned. The stress-free configuration is considered as a Riemannian manifold that is not Euclidean. A strain energy function is adopted to analyze stresses. Torque is linearly related to torsion of vessel axis under a physiological condition. The shear component of deformation gradient almost linearly increases from the inner surface of vessel to the outer surface with discontinuity at the boundary between media and adventitia. The shear stress also increases from the inner surface to the outer surface. The shear stress is greatly larger in the adventitia than in the media-intima.

Keywords: Torsion of Artery, Two-layer model, Residual stresses, Three-dimensional Riemannian stress-free configuration

1. Introduction

Torques induced by torsions around vessel axis have been observed in arteries [1, 2]. It is shown that the torques linearly depend on the torsional angle at constant intraluminal pressures and axial stretch ratios. Lu et al. [1] and Sommer et al. [2] analyze their experiments using a two-layer model. The data are explained by the linear theory of elasticity. The shear elastic modulus depends on the axial stretch ratio in their articles. A nonlinear elastic theory using a strain energy function should be applied to explain the relationship between torque and torsion around the vessel axis. Desyatova et al. deal with the torsion of the human femoropopliteal artery in the clinical measurements [3]. They analyze strain and stress in the one-layer model by the nonlinear theory using strain energy function.

On the other hand, the author introduced a Riemannian stress-free configuration considering residual deformations of ring radially cut and axial strip sectioned from vessel [4]. This is appropriate to a nonlinear elasticity based on the large deformation theory. For example, it seems to be useful for analyses of data in articles by Sommer et al. [2] and Sommer and Holzapfel [5] because their studies include sufficient experimental data to determine Riemannian stress-free configurations. The residual stress in remodeling and growth of arterial walls is discussed by Fung [6], Humphrey [7], and Lubarda and Hoger [8]. The concept of Riemannian stress-free configuration is valid for theories of remodeling and growth mechanics.

Analyses on strain and stress distributions in arteries have been performed by many researchers [9-13] but there have been few studies on the case of existence of shear strains [13]. The author analyzes the shear stress distributions in a human arterial wall based on the two-layer model considering the residual stresses due to the circumferential and axial residual deformations under physiologically pressurized conditions with a strain energy function proposed in articles [14, 15]. There is a study in which a three-layer model is used for the human aortae considering the residual stresses [11] although the shear strain with a torsion is not considered. The present analysis describes the shear stress distributions in an arterial wall induced by torsions under the physiological intraluminal pressure 13.33 kPa (100 mmHg) and axial stretch ratios 1.05, 1.10, 1.15 and 1.20 with reference to the unloaded configuration.

2. Methods

2.1. Kinematics

There may not be a global stress-free configuration if a material body is subject to residual stress. There are, however, local stress-free configurations because an infinitesimally small body sectioned from the whole body without external forces must be stress free. This consideration introduces a Riemannian stress-free configuration [16].

Let a set of material points of a solid body be B and three-dimensional Euclidean space be E^3 . A mapping $\chi: B \rightarrow E^3$ is called a current configuration following Truesdell and Noll [17].

Fig. 1 Schematic drawings of local stress-free arcs and unloaded vessels of media-intima and adventitia and loaded intact vessel are shown. The arcs theoretically are infinitesimally thin. The axial length of vessel should be regarded as one between the two marks to determine the elongation, not the length between two sutures that fix the vessel at the cannulas of the experimental apparatus.

For a stress-free configuration κ we define coordinates of a material point $p \in B$ by a curvilinear coordinate system $\mathbf{X} = [X^1 X^2 X^3] = \kappa(p)$ with (a, b) components G_{ab} of metric tensor. We represent a matrix of components of metric tensor by $\mathbf{G} = [G_{ab}]$ which is symmetric and the determinant of $G = \det \mathbf{G}$, and so on. The distance that is infinitesimally close two material points in the stress-free solid body of an artery in Fig. 1 may be defined as follows:

$$d\mathcal{S}^2 = G_{ab} dX^a dX^b = R^2 d\Theta^2 + S^2 d\Psi^2 + dR^2 \quad (1)$$

For the current configuration χ we define coordinates $\mathbf{x} = [x^1 x^2 x^3] = \chi(p)$ with components of metric tensor g_{ab} in E^3 . Each component is $x^a = x^a(p) = x^a(\kappa^{-1}(\mathbf{X}))$. The deformation gradient of χ with reference to κ is defined as follows:

$$\mathbf{F} = \left[\frac{\partial x^a}{\partial X^b} \right] \quad (2)$$

where $\partial x^a / \partial X^b$ represents (a, b) component of the matrix which is a two-point tensor. If the material is incompressible, $\sqrt{g} \det \mathbf{F} = \sqrt{G}$ is satisfied [18]. The Green-Lagrange strain tensor of the current configuration with reference to the stress-free body is provided as follows:

$$\mathbf{E} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{g} \mathbf{F} - \mathbf{G}) \quad (3)$$

Because we treat the cylindrical tube of artery, we choose the cylindrical coordinate system as follows:

$$\mathbf{x} = [x^1 \ x^2 \ x^3] = [\theta \ z \ r], \quad \mathbf{g} = \begin{bmatrix} r^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{current configuration}) \quad (4)$$

Local stress-free configurations for media-intima and adventitia are shown in Fig. 1. These are idealized configurations for simplicity. We assume that the infinitesimally thin sliced sectors and narrow curled axial strips are stress free. The coordinate system compatible with the local stress-free configurations may be introduced as follows:

$$\mathbf{X} = [X^1 \ X^2 \ X^3] = [\Theta \ \Psi \ R], \quad \mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} R^2 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & S^2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (S = S_i + R_i - R) \quad (5)$$

where $\Theta \in [0, \Theta_0]$, $\Psi \in [0, \Psi_0]$, $R \in [R_i, R_o]$, and $S \in [S_o, S_i]$. The dimensions of the stress-free configurations of media-intima and adventitia are shown in Table 1 based on the article [14]. It should be noted that Ψ_0 depends on the axial length of specimen determined in the experiment. Quantity of Ψ_0 / l_u (l_u denotes the axial length of the unloaded specimen) is independent of the axial length of specimen.

Table 1 Dimensions of local stress-free arcs (*M*: Media-intima, *A*: Adventitia). These values are estimated from the means with specimens [19].

R_{Mi} (mm)	R_{Mo} (mm)	Θ_{M0} (rad)	S_{Mi} (mm)	Ψ_{M0} (rad)
5.567	6.267	3.462	71.779	0.214
R_{Ai} (mm)	R_{Ao} (mm)	Θ_{A0} (rad)	S_{Ai} (mm)	Ψ_{A0} (rad)
3.949	4.419	5.654	8.235	1.736

In the following, the sub- and super-scripts of tensor components will be often represented with symbols of Θ , Ψ , R , θ , z , r instead of the integers of 1, 2, 3. The independent six covariant components of the Riemann curvature tensor are $\mathcal{R}_{\Theta\Psi\Theta\Psi}$, $\mathcal{R}_{R\Theta R\Theta}$, $\mathcal{R}_{\Psi R \Psi R}$, $\mathcal{R}_{\Theta\Psi\Theta R}$, $\mathcal{R}_{\Psi\Theta\Psi R}$, $\mathcal{R}_{R\Theta R\Psi}$ in a three-dimensional manifold [18]. A component of Riemann curvature tensor is given as follows:

$$\mathcal{R}_{\Theta\Psi\Theta\Psi} = RS > 0 \quad (6)$$

The other five components vanish all over the stress-free configurations for media-intima and adventitia. The Riemann curvature tensor does not vanish as shown in Eq. (6), i.e., the Riemannian stress-free configurations for media-intima and adventitia are non-Euclidean in the case that the circumferential ring opens by a radial cut and the axial strip curls. This implies that there are no global stress-free configurations compatible with the experimental data embedded in three-dimensional Euclidean space. In addition, there are mathematical possibilities that R and S take plus, minus and infinite values depending on the shape of circumferential and axial arcs.

We consider a deformation of $\theta = (2\pi/\Theta_{L0})\Theta_L$, $z = (l_z/\Psi_{L0})\Psi_L$, $r = r(R_L)$. The deformation gradient of a configuration under pressurization and an axial stretch with reference to the Riemannian stress-free configuration is expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_{1L} = \left[\frac{\partial x^a}{\partial X_L^b} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2\pi}{\Theta_{L0}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_z}{\Psi_{L0}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{dr}{dR_L} \end{bmatrix} \quad (7)$$

where L denotes M (Media-intima) or A (Adventitia). The deformation gradient expressed by the physical components is as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{F}}_{1L} &= \left[\sqrt{g_{aa}} \sqrt{G^{bb}} \frac{\partial x^a}{\partial X_L^b} \right] = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2\pi r}{\Theta_{L0} R_L} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_z}{\Psi_{L0} S_L} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{dr}{dR_L} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{not sum with } a, b) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_\theta & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_z & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_r \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

where the media-intima wall is indicated by $L=M$ and the adventitial one $L=A$ and l_z is a segment length of the current configuration extended arbitrarily. There may be stretch and stress discontinuities at the boundary between the media-intima and adventitia layers.

The uniform torsion around vessel axis is expressed with $\theta' = \theta + \gamma z$, $z' = z$, and $r' = r$. The deformation gradient is expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_2 = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (9)$$

The total deformation is as follows:

$$\mathbf{F}_L = \mathbf{F}_2 \mathbf{F}_{1L} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2\pi}{\Theta_{L0}} & \frac{l_z}{\Psi_{L0}} \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_z}{\Psi_{L0}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{dr}{dR_L} \end{bmatrix} \quad (10)$$

The physical components are as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\mathbf{F}}_L = \left[\sqrt{g_{aa}} \sqrt{G_L^{bb}} F_{Lb}^a \right] &= \begin{bmatrix} \frac{2\pi r}{\Theta_{L0} R_L} & \frac{l_z r}{\Psi_{L0} S_L} \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & \frac{l_z}{\Psi_{L0} S_L} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \frac{dr}{dR_L} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{not sum with } a, b) \\ &= \begin{bmatrix} \lambda_\theta & \lambda_z r \gamma & 0 \\ 0 & \lambda_z & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & \lambda_r \end{bmatrix} \end{aligned} \quad (11)$$

The incompressibility condition $\sqrt{g} \det \mathbf{F}_L = \sqrt{G_L}$ of the wall provides the following relationship:

$$\frac{2\pi r}{\Theta_{L0} R_L} \frac{l_z}{\Psi_{L0} S_L} \frac{dr}{dR_L} = 1 \quad (S_{Li} - S_L = R_L - R_{Li}) \quad (12)$$

The radius r of a material point position in the wall of the current configuration is provided as follows:

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{\Theta_{M0} \Psi_{M0}}{6\pi \tilde{\lambda}_z l_u} \left[-2R_M^3 + 3(R_{Mi} + S_{Mi})R_M^2 - (R_{Mi} + 3S_{Mi})R_{Mi}^2 \right] + r_i^2} \quad (R_M \in [R_{Mi}, R_{Mo}])$$

$$r = \sqrt{\frac{\Theta_{A0} \Psi_{A0}}{6\pi \tilde{\lambda}_z l_u} \left[-2R_A^3 + 3(R_{Ai} + S_{Ai})R_A^2 - (R_{Ai} + 3S_{Ai})R_{Ai}^2 \right] + r_m^2} \quad (R_A \in [R_{Ai}, R_{Ao}]) \quad (13)$$

where the radius $r_m = r(R_{Mo})$ is calculated with the first equation in Eq. (13). In this case, there is not any gap or overlap between the media and adventitia layers. Because l_z can be expressed by the axial stretch ratio $\tilde{\lambda}_z$ with reference to the axial length of unloaded intact artery, we use a relationship $l_z = \tilde{\lambda}_z l_u$ ($l_u \approx 15.0$ mm). The diagonal stretch ratios with reference to the stress-free configurations are denoted with λ_θ , λ_z , and λ_r .

2.2. Strain energy function

We use the strain energy function [15] to characterize the vessel layers as follows:

$$W = \frac{\mu}{2}(I-3) + \frac{k_1}{2k_2} \sum_{a=+,-} (\exp(k_2 \psi_a) - 1), \quad \psi_\pm = (1-\zeta)(I-3)^2 + \zeta(K_\pm - 1)^2$$

$$I = Tr(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{g} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{G}^{-1}), \quad K_\pm = Tr(\mathbf{F}^T \mathbf{g} \mathbf{F} \mathbf{V}_\pm^T \mathbf{V}_\pm) \quad (14)$$

where μ and k_1 denote constants with energy density dimension, k_2 and ζ are nondimensional constants, and the two unit contravariant vectors $\mathbf{v}_\pm = [v_\pm^\theta \ v_\pm^z \ v_\pm^r]$ in the Riemannian stress-free configuration ($G_{ab} v_\pm^a v_\pm^b = 1$) are defined by $V_\pm^a = \bar{V}_\pm^a / \sqrt{G_{aa}}$ (not sum with a): $\bar{\mathbf{V}}_+ = [\cos \varphi \ \sin \varphi \ 0]$ and $\bar{\mathbf{V}}_- = [\cos(-\varphi) \ \sin(-\varphi) \ 0]$ in which $\pm \varphi$ denote angles of fibers against the circumferential direction with peak frequencies of a symmetric bimodal distribution although these angles are not determined by histological observations, and $Tr(\bullet)$ represents a trace of matrix and, therefore, I and K_\pm are invariant. The weight $\zeta \in [0, 1]$ is one of fiber components in the exponential term. In the present study \mathbf{F} includes non-zero shear strain, and the strain energy function has the cylindrical orthotropic symmetry [20]. If there is not the shear strain, + and - terms are the same in Eq. (14). Because the physical components of deformation gradient may be expressed with λ_θ , λ_z , λ_r , γ , I and K_\pm in the cylindrical coordinates are expressed as follows:

$$I = Tr(\bar{\mathbf{F}}^T \bar{\mathbf{F}}) = \lambda_\theta^2 + (1+r^2\gamma^2)\lambda_z^2 + \lambda_r^2$$

$$K_\pm = Tr(\bar{\mathbf{F}}^T \bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{V}}_\pm^T \bar{\mathbf{V}}_\pm) = (\bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{V}}_\pm^T) \cdot (\bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{V}}_\pm^T) = \lambda_\theta^2 \cos^2 \varphi \pm 2\lambda_\theta \lambda_z r \gamma \cos \varphi \sin \varphi + (1+r^2\gamma^2)\lambda_z^2 \sin^2 \varphi \quad (15)$$

Here, column vectors $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_\pm^T = \bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{V}}_\pm^T$ are vectors deformed from the unit vectors $\bar{\mathbf{V}}_\pm^T$ along fiber directions. Therefore, the inner products $\bar{\mathbf{v}}_\pm^T \cdot \bar{\mathbf{v}}_\pm^T$ represent squares of stretch ratios of fibers. Considering that fibers support only tension under stretched condition, K_\pm which are squares of stretch ratios of $+\varphi$ and $-\varphi$ fibers are set 1 when they are smaller than 1

in computing.

The values of material parameters used in the present paper are shown in Table 2 for the separated media-intima and adventitia based on the literature [5]. Although the media-intima layer may not be regarded as a homogeneous layer, the author treated it as one homogeneous layer because the experimental data were limited [5, 19].

Table 2 Mean material parameters of strain energy function are used for the media-intima and the adventitia [5]. It is assumed that the media-intima layer is homogeneous although it is not correct.

	μ (kPa)	k_1 (kPa)	k_2	ζ	φ (rad)
<i>Media-intima</i>	122.3	24.7	16.5	0.8	0.183
<i>Adventitia</i>	59.6	180.9	109.8	0.8	0.525

2.3. Cauchy stress

The Cauchy stress tensor for the incompressible material can be derived from the strain energy function as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\tau} = -H\mathbf{g} + \mathbf{g}\mathbf{F} \frac{\partial W}{\partial \mathbf{F}} \quad (16)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau} = [\tau_{ab}]$ and H denote a matrix of components of the Cauchy stress and a Lagrange multiplier for the incompressibility of the material, respectively, and the (a, b) component of $\partial W / \partial \mathbf{F}$ is defined as $\partial W / \partial F_a^b$.

2.4. Equilibrium equation of Cauchy stress in the cylindrical coordinate system

The orthogonal unit vectors of coordinate bases are expressed as follows:

$$\mathbf{a}_\theta = -\mathbf{a}_x \sin \theta + \mathbf{a}_y \cos \theta, \quad \mathbf{a}_z = \mathbf{a}_z, \quad \mathbf{a}_r = \mathbf{a}_x \cos \theta + \mathbf{a}_y \sin \theta \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{a}^\theta = \mathbf{a}_\theta, \quad \mathbf{a}^z = \mathbf{a}_z, \quad \mathbf{a}^r = \mathbf{a}_r$$

Here, $\partial \mathbf{a}_\theta / \partial \theta = -\mathbf{a}_r$, $\partial \mathbf{a}_r / \partial \theta = \mathbf{a}_\theta$ and the others vanish. Del for the cylindrical coordinate system is as follows:

$$\nabla = \mathbf{a}^\theta \frac{\partial}{r \partial \theta} + \mathbf{a}^z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} + \mathbf{a}^r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \quad (18)$$

Because the physical components of the stress are $[\sigma_{ab}] = [\sqrt{g^{aa}} \sqrt{g^{bb}} \tau_{ab}]$ (not sum with a , b), the equilibrium equation for the physical components is as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = \sigma_{ab} \mathbf{a}^a \otimes \mathbf{a}^b = \sigma^{ab} \mathbf{a}_a \otimes \mathbf{a}_b = \sigma_a^b \mathbf{a}^a \otimes \mathbf{a}_b$$

$$\text{div } \boldsymbol{\sigma} = \nabla \cdot (\sigma^{ab} \mathbf{a}_a \otimes \mathbf{a}_b) = \left(\mathbf{a}_\theta \frac{\partial}{r \partial \theta} + \mathbf{a}_z \frac{\partial}{\partial z} + \mathbf{a}_r \frac{\partial}{\partial r} \right) \cdot (\sigma_{ab} \mathbf{a}_a \otimes \mathbf{a}_b) = \mathbf{0} \quad (19)$$

where $\mathbf{0}$ on the right-hand side represents zero vector and $\mathbf{a}_a \cdot (\mathbf{a}_b \otimes \mathbf{a}_c) = \delta_{ab} \mathbf{a}_c$, $(\partial / \partial x^a)(\mathbf{a}_b \otimes \mathbf{a}_c) = (\partial \mathbf{a}_b / \partial x^a) \otimes \mathbf{a}_c + \mathbf{a}_b \otimes (\partial \mathbf{a}_c / \partial x^a)$.

The Cauchy stress may be also expressed from Eq. (16) for an orthogonal curvilinear coordinate system as follows:

$$\boldsymbol{\sigma} = -H\mathbf{I} + \bar{\mathbf{F}} \frac{\partial W}{\partial \bar{\mathbf{F}}}$$

$$= -H\mathbf{I} + \mu \bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{F}}^T + 2k_1(1-\zeta)(I-3) \sum_{a=+,-} \exp(k_2 \psi_a) \bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{F}}^T + 2k_1 \zeta \sum_{a=+,-} (K_a - 1) \exp(k_2 \psi_a) \bar{\mathbf{F}} \bar{\mathbf{V}}_a^T \bar{\mathbf{V}}_a \bar{\mathbf{F}}^T \quad (20)$$

where \mathbf{I} denotes the three-dimensional unit matrix. In the present study, only the following equation is nontrivial:

$$\frac{d\sigma_{rr}}{dr} + \frac{\sigma_{rr} - \sigma_{\theta\theta}}{r} = 0 \quad (21)$$

Here, the boundary conditions are $\sigma_{rr}(r_i) = -P_i$, $\sigma_{rr}(r_m - o) = \sigma_{rr}(r_m + o)$ for an infinitesimally small positive number o , and $\sigma_{rr}(r_o) = -P_o = 0$. We can obtain the following relationships:

$$P_i = \int_{r_i}^{r_o} (\sigma_{\theta\theta} - \sigma_{rr}) \frac{dr}{r}$$

$$F_z = -\pi r_i^2 P_i + 2\pi \int_{r_i}^{r_o} \sigma_{zz} r dr$$

$$M_z = 2\pi \int_{r_i}^{r_o} \sigma_{\theta z} r^2 dr \quad (22)$$

where P_i , F_z and M_z denote the intraluminal pressure, axial force and torque around the vessel axis, respectively. The above integrals include the discontinuities of integrands at the radius of r_m which is the boundary between media and adventitia.

3. Results

3.1 Torque with shear strain

The torques around the vessel axis on the axial torsion per unit axial length γ at the intraluminal pressure 13.33 kPa (100 mmHg) and the axial stretch ratios 1.05, 1.10, 1.15 and 1.20 with reference to the unloaded configuration are shown in Fig. 2. The torques are almost linearly related to axial torsion. The dependency of calculated results coincides with that of the experimental results [1, 2] although the parameters of the strain energy function are determined without torsional tests [5].

Fig. 2 Torque around vessel axis (a) and axial force (b) at intraluminal pressure 13.33 kPa and axial stretch ratios 1.05, 1.10, 1.15 and 1.20 on torsional angle per unit length γ .

The material parameters for the adventitia are different from the parameters used in the previous work [21] because it is intended to cover the range of supraphysiological pressures although the present study treats only the physiological region. See references [5, 21] on the orthogonal experimental and calculated results. The author also calculated the torques and the stresses in the arterial wall using the parameters determined in the supraphysiological region [5]. The torques and shear stress were lower with the parameters determined in the supraphysiological experimental data [5, 21] than those calculated with the parameters determined by the physiological experiments [5] although the pattern of stress distributions did not change. The author thinks that the pattern of the distribution of shear stress is robust on the parameters of the strain energy function. This robustness is also the same as the variability of parameters with various specimens. The important point seems to be the extremely high values of k_1 and k_2 for the adventitia as shown in Table 2. Linear relationships between torque and torsion are obtained with variable sets of parameters [5].

3.2 Shear strain and stress distributions

Calculated results of distributions of a shear component $\bar{F}_\Psi^\theta = \lambda_z r \gamma$ of the deformation gradient and a shear component $\sigma_{\theta z}$ of the Cauchy stress in the arterial wall are shown in Fig. 3. These increase from the inner surface of the artery to the outer surface. The shear component of the deformation gradient \bar{F}_Ψ^θ has a discontinuity at the boundary between the media and the adventitia because λ_z is discontinuous at the boundary between the media and the adventitia. The shear component of stress is small in the media-intima layer due to small stiffness compared to that in the adventitia as same as the diagonal stresses [21].

Fig. 3 Shear deformation \bar{F}_Ψ^θ (a) and Cauchy stress $\sigma_{\theta z}$ (b) at intraluminal pressure 13.33 kPa, torsion 0.005 rad/mm and axial stretch ratios 1.05, 1.10, 1.15 and 1.20.

4. Discussions

The relationships of torque vs torsion are linear under physiological conditions even though a nonlinear constitutive law is used with the strain energy function. The reason is considered that we treated low shear strains compared to the diagonal components, i.e., the results for shear strain and stress are in the region of linear approximation of the strain energy function although the shear stress shows a nonlinearity in the adventitia (Fig. 3 (b)). In large axial stretch ratio, the relationship of torque vs torsion shows nonlinearity (not shown) although it is not physiological. Change of relationship of torque vs torsion depending on the axial stretch seems to be small compared to the experimental results [1, 2]. This is from the parameters of strain energy function derived from experiments without torsions [5]. The author could not obtain the data of residual deformations from the torsional experiments [1, 2].

The discontinuities in the shear component of deformation gradient in Fig. 3 (a) are due to discontinuities of distribution of axial stretch ratio λ_z at the boundary between the media and adventitia (see Eq. (11)) although the term of $r\gamma$ which is twice of shear strain in the small strain theory assuming no residual strains [1] is continuous on a radius of r .

Relationships of torque vs torsion show a slight asymmetry depending on direction of rotation [1, 2]. This implies that the distribution of orientation of fibers (collagen, elastin and smooth muscle) is not symmetric despite a result of mechanical properties by Patel et al. [20]. In the present study, symmetric distribution was assumed, i.e. the angles of peaks of fiber orientations are assumed $\pm\varphi$.

The applicability of the present study to the clinical case [3] is an interesting subject. The problem is to determine stress-free configuration. The determination of stress-free arcs is impossible in the clinical case. Therefore, it is realistic to avoid determination of stress-free state. Only the method adopted by Desyatova et al. [3] is possible one in the present situation although the present theory considers an axial arc as a local stress-free state which has a finite curvature to define an axial coordinate. This axial coordinate Ψ may not be defined as a non-curved axial strip. Therefore, the present theory is not applicable to the ordinary non-curved stress-free configuration assumed.

5. Conclusion

The experimental results of linear relationship between torque and torsion around the vessel axis are well explained by a strain energy function obtained by orthogonal loading experiments of arteries. This result is obtained from the fact that the shear strain with torsions around the vessel axis is small compared to the diagonal strains. At higher axial stretch ratios over physiological conditions, the calculated results show nonlinear relationships of torque vs torsion (not shown).

Declaration of competing interests

The author declares that he has no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper. This research did not receive any specific grant from funding agencies in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

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